

RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF NON-SEPTAL ACCESSORY PATHWAYS

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Abstract. Purpose. For patients experiencing symptomatic supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) due to accessory pathways (APs), catheter ablation is a Class I indicated therapy. Our study was aimed to compare the success and recurrence rates and the procedure time spent on radiofrequency ablation (RFA) when using irrigated or non-irrigated catheters.

Material and methods: This was a retrospective and prospective study of 129 patients who underwent RFA of non-septal APs between April 2009 and January 2019.

Results: There was no significant difference in the success rate of ablations and recurrences when comparing non-irrigated and irrigated catheters. Left-sided APs were ablated significantly more successfully than right-sided pathways. Procedure and fluoroscopy time were considerably longer when utilising non-irrigated catheters versus irrigated ones, however, there was no substantial difference in ablation time between the 2 groups. Moreover, the recurrence rate did not significantly differ between the studied groups.

Conclusion: The findings of this research can contribute to improving the management of patients with APs and enrich limited data on catheter ablation of APs with different types of catheters in the adult population.

Keywords: accessory pathways, irrigated catheters, non-irrigated catheters, radiofrequency ablation.

Introduction

In the normal heart, only the atrioventricular (AV) node is capable to conduct of electrical impulses from the atria to the ventricle. In the presence of an AP, an electrical impulse can pass using both an AV node and an AP, but at different speeds (1,2). APs are muscle threads connecting the myocardium of the atria and ventricles, which are capable of conducting an electrical impulse

via APs retrogradely (from the ventricle to the atrium), anterogradely (from the atrium to the ventricle), or both (1). These extranodal pathways are congenital and caused by insufficient AV annular isolation during embryological development. Both junctions, the AV node and an AP with slow and fast conduction, respectively, contribute to the onset of atrioventricular reentry tachycardia (AVRT) (2).

For patients experiencing symptomatic SVT due to APs, catheter ablation is a Class I indicated therapy (1,3). This strategy has a success rate of over 95% and a minimal risk of complications (1). Many arrhythmias can be successfully ablated; however, ablation failures can occur for different reasons, particularly insufficient ablation energy delivery. Catheter irrigation is one of the ways to address this issue. It has been established that irrigated ablation catheters are safer and more effective than non-irrigated catheters for treating atrial flutter (4,5), atrial fibrillation (AF) (6), and ventricular tachycardia (7). However, there is a dearth of information regarding the usage of irrigated catheters for APs ablation in the adult population. This study was aimed to evaluate success and recurrence rates, procedure, fluoroscopy, and ablation times when RFA of non-septal APs was performed using irrigated versus non-irrigated catheters.

Material and methods

Data on all RFA of APs carried out by the same team of operators at the single institution was collected and analyzed, both retrospectively and prospectively. Informed consent was obtained from prospectively recruited patients.

The study included adult patients who underwent RFA of AP for the first time between April 2009 and January 2019. Concealed APs were established during the electrophysiological (EP) study, while manifest APs were diagnosed from the baseline electrocardiography (ECG). Patients with septal and multiple APs were excluded from this study. Information including patients' age and sex along with procedural data such as procedure duration, ablation and fluoroscopy times, procedural success, catheter type, AP characteristics and location were gathered. Five-year follow-up was performed to assess and compare recurrences in both groups.

Description of the procedure

Right femoral and internal jugular accesses were used for EP study and ablation. All patients were in a mildly sedated state during the procedure. The quadripolar diagnostic catheter (AVAIL Quadripolar Fixed Shape Catheter, Biosense Webster, CA, USA) was positioned apically in the right ventricle. A decapolar diagnostic catheter (WEBSTER Decapolar Catheter Fixed, Biosense Webster, CA, USA) was inserted via the right internal jugular vein into the coronary sinus.

Manual catheter navigation (MCN) was utilised to guide ablation catheters. Standard handheld deflectable ablation catheters were used to perform ablation.

During the EP study, we conducted mapping using an ablation catheter and the earliest activation of the ventricles was determined. When this activation was detected on the intracardiac electrogram of the ablation catheter, RFA was performed at this location.

Ablation and Catheters

A 3.5 mm tip externally irrigated catheter (Celsius ThermoCool electrophysiology catheter, Biosense Webster, CA, USA) was used to perform irrigated ablation at a maximum power of 40 W for 60-90 seconds. Using a 4-mm catheter (Celsius electrophysiology catheter, Biosense

Webster, CA, USA), non-irrigated ablation (temperature-controlled mode) was carried out at 55–60 °C for 60–90 seconds with a power of 30–60 W.

The absence of both retrograde and antegrade AP conductions during the EP study following a waiting period (30 minutes) at the end of ablation was considered a procedural success.

Statistics

Procedural success, ablation time, fluoroscopy time, and overall procedure time were all analysed for each case, stratified by type of catheter. GraphPad Prism 9 and Microsoft Excel 2013 were used for statistical analysis. The mean \pm standard deviation (SD) was used to present continuous data. A percentage was used to display categorical data. The unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test was utilised to compare continuous data. When necessary, Fisher's exact test or chi-square was used to ascertain the link between the categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

IRB approval

This study was conducted in compliance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. The study's protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB no. 8). Informed consent was obtained from all prospectively recruited patients participating in the study.

Results

Patients

The analysis was conducted on 129 initial APs ablations. Patients were divided into 2 representative groups: group 1 - patients who underwent RFA with irrigated catheters, and group 2 – patients who ablated with non-irrigated catheters. Of the patients, irrigated catheters were utilised for 67 (51.9%), while non-irrigated catheters for 62 (48.1%). Ablation catheters in 129 cases (100%) were driven with MCN. The mean age was 33.6 ± 13.9 and 33.1 ± 13.1 years in groups 1 and 2 ($p=0.85$), respectively. Group 1 included 33 (49.3%) females and 34 (50.7%) males, while group 2 – 23 (37.1%) females and 39 (62.9%) males ($p=0.21$).

All patients did not experience any acute complications.

Characteristics and success of procedures based on accessory pathway location

There were 91 left-sided (70.5%;) and 38 right-sided APs (29.5%;). Overall success rates were 98.9% (90/91) and 86.8% (33/38) for left-sided and right-sided APs ablation regardless of the type of catheter, respectively. In this study, the difference in success rates depending on AP location (left-sided and right-sided) was significant ($p=0.009$;). Among all 129 APs ablations, there was no distinction in success rate between non-irrigated catheters (58/62, 93.5%) and irrigated catheters (65/67, 97%; $p=0.43$;).

There were no significant differences in success rates when these rates were analysed separately for left-sided and right-sided APs ablations with different types of catheters. The success rates of ablation of right-sided APs were 91.3% (21/23) and 80% (12/15) in groups 1 and 2, respectively ($p=0.36$). Ablation of left-sided APs was successful in all cases (44/44) with irrigated catheters and 97.9% of cases (46/47) with non-irrigated catheters ($p>0.99$).

This study included catheter ablations of 98 (76%) manifest and 31 (24%) concealed APs. There was no significant difference in the overall success rate when comparing ablations of manifest (94/98, 96%) and concealed (29/31, 93.5%; $p=0.63$) APs.

Procedure time was significantly distinct when comparing irrigated catheters (99.8 ± 32.1 min) versus non-irrigated (126.4 ± 37.2 min; $p<0.0001$;). A similar tendency was observed for fluoroscopy time. The mean fluoroscopy time was 13.3 ± 1.9 min when using irrigated catheters

and 20.6 ± 2.4 min when utilising non-irrigated ones ($p < 0.0001$;). However, there was no significant difference in ablation time between groups 1 (3.2 ± 0.9 min) and 2 (3.4 ± 0.8 min; $p = 0.09$;). Further, we compared the procedure, fluoroscopy, and ablation time spent by irrigated and non-irrigated catheters for ablation of manifest, concealed, right-sided, and left-sided APs separately.

In all cases procedure and fluoroscopy times were significantly shorter when using irrigated catheters compared to non-irrigated ones.

Five-year follow-up demonstrated that recurrences were observed in 2 cases when using irrigated catheters (2/67, 3%) and in 4 patients when using non-irrigated catheters (4/62, 6.4%; $p = 0.43$).

Discussion

This study revealed the following principal findings:

1. Ablation of left-sided APs was more effective compared to right-sided APs according to overall success rate.
2. There were no significant differences in success rates when these rates were compared separately for manifest, concealed, left-sided and right-sided APs ablations with different types of catheters.
3. Procedure and fluoroscopy time were significantly longer when using non-irrigated catheters compared to irrigated ones.
4. There was no significant difference in recurrences during the five-year follow-up between 2 groups, although they were more frequently observed when using non-irrigated catheters.

These findings echo previous research that demonstrated difficulties in ablation of right-sided APs compared to the left-sided ones. These difficulties can be explained by the tricuspid valve anatomy and catheter placement stability (8).

In our study percentage of overall success was lower for non-irrigated catheters compared to irrigated, even though it was not significant. Previous studies compared irrigated and non-irrigated catheters in ventricular tachycardia, AF, and atrial flutter ablations (4-7). Irrigated catheters have been demonstrated to be more effective and safe in ablation of typical atrial flutter. Moreover, fluoroscopy and procedure time were decreased in the cavotricuspid isthmus ablation (4,5). A similar tendency in terms of effectiveness and safety was observed in pulmonary vein isolation. In addition, usage of irrigated catheters was associated with an increased rate of sinus rhythm maintenance after ablation of AF (6). The ablation of APs in the adult population, in contrast to the pediatric population, has not been studied enough (9-12).

Although only MCN was used in this study, prior studies also compared fluoroscopy and procedure time during AP ablation with MCN versus remote magnetic navigation (RMN). MCN has been shown to be equal or inferior to RMN in terms of safety and fluoroscopic exposure to the operator and patient (12).

A recent study retrospectively analysed AP ablations in the adult population and demonstrated that the success rate was considerably higher in ablations utilising irrigated catheters. Moreover, fluoroscopy time during the procedure was significantly shorter when using the irrigated catheters (9), which coincides with the data obtained in our study.

Often, most ablations with a non-irrigated catheter are performed in the septal area to avoid the risk of AV block (13). This is one of the reasons why only non-septal APs were included in this study.

A three-dimensional mapping/navigation system was not used for any of the ablations, which was a study limitation.

Conclusion

The findings of this research can contribute to improve management of patients with APs and enrich limited data on catheter ablation of APs with different types of catheters in the adult population.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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